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Bug P2 + Add Hotlist

STATUS UPDATE No update yet.

DESCRIPTION ai...@gmail.com created issue #1 Mar 19, 2026 04:04PM

When attempting to verify a malformed APK, apksigner verify completely crashes due to an unhandled ZipFormatException rather than rejecting the APK and returning a standard DOES NOT VERIFY response.

This is due to a compressed size mismatch between the LFH and the CD for AndroidManifest.xml. While it is correct for apksig to reject this file strictly, the exception is not trapped, causing the entire utility to crash with a Java stack trace.

Standard extraction tools like unzip are able to successfully extract the files from this exact same APK, indicating that the crash is specific to apksig's ZIP parser failing to catch its own format exceptions.

Environment:

- OS: Ubuntu 22.04
Java: OpenJDK 17
apksigner version: 0.9

Steps to Reproduce:

- Download the attached malformed APK (F-Droid_malformed.apk).
Run the verification command:

```
apksigner verify F-Droid_malformed.apk
```

Expected Result: The tool should exit gracefully with a non-zero status code and print a clear error message, such as:

```
DOES NOT VERIFY
ERROR: APK integrity check failed. ZipFormatException: Compressed size mismatch...
```

Actual Result: The tool crashes entirely with the following unhandled exception:

```
Exception in thread "main" com.android.apksig.apk.ApkFormatException: Failed to read AndroidManifest.xml
at com.android.apksig.ApkVerifier.getAndroidManifestFromApk(ApkVerifier.java:985)
at com.android.apksig.ApkVerifier.verifyAndGetMinSdkVersion(ApkVerifier.java:587)
at com.android.apksig.ApkVerifier.verify(ApkVerifier.java:181)
at com.android.apksig.ApkVerifier.verify(ApkVerifier.java:149)
at com.android.apksigner.ApkSignerTool.verify(ApkSignerTool.java:516)
at com.android.apksigner.ApkSignerTool.main(ApkSignerTool.java:88)
Caused by: com.android.apksig.zip.ZipFormatException: Compressed size mismatch between Local File Header and Central Directory for entry AndroidManifest.xml. LFH: 4268761, CD: 8921
at com.android.apksig.internal.zip.LocalFileRecord.getRecord(LocalFileRecord.java:198)
at com.android.apksig.internal.zip.LocalFileRecord.outputUncompressedData(LocalFileRecord.java:427)
at com.android.apksig.internal.zip.LocalFileRecord.getUncompressedData(LocalFileRecord.java:451)
at com.android.apksig.ApkSigner.getAndroidManifestFromApk(ApkSigner.java:902)
at com.android.apksig.ApkVerifier.getAndroidManifestFromApk(ApkVerifier.java:981)
... 5 more
```

Note: As evidence that the underlying zip data is mostly intact and the crash is parser-specific, running standard unzip F-Droid_malformed.apk successfully extracts AndroidManifest.xml and the rest of the payload without crashing.

F-Droid_malformed.apk 12 MB Download

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